

Risk Factors for Pancreatic Cancer and Their Impact on Survival and Prognosis in Algerian Population

Rahima Amarouche ✉

Medical Oncology Department, Pierre and Marie Curie Center, Algiers, Algeria;
University of Health Sciences, Algiers, Algeria

Esma Kerboua

Medical Oncology Department, Pierre and Marie Curie Center, Algiers, Algeria;
University of Health Sciences, Algiers, Algeria

Merzek Gharnaout

University of Health Sciences, Algiers, Algeria; Pulmonology and Phthiisology
Department, Beni Messous University Hospital Center, Algeria

Abstract

Pancreatic cancer, predominantly represented by pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC), is among the most severe malignancies and remains one of the most aggressive tumors worldwide. It ranks among the five leading causes of cancer-related mortality and exhibits the lowest survival rate of all cancers. Reported one-year and five-year survival rates are approximately 20% and less than 5%, respectively. Its incidence continues to rise, particularly among women and younger populations. Diagnosis is often delayed due to non-specific and poorly suggestive symptoms, which largely explains its unfavorable prognosis. Numerous modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors have been identified and play a decisive role in both disease incidence and clinical progression. This article aims to present the main risk factors for exocrine pancreatic cancer and to analyze their impact on patient survival and prognosis.

Introduction

Pancreatic cancer represents a major public health challenge due to its high mortality rate and the lack of effective screening strategies in the general population [1]. It is currently the fourth leading cause of cancer-related death in industrialized countries [2]. Identifying risk factors not only improves the understanding of disease pathophysiology but also enhances prevention strategies, early diagnosis, and prognostic assessment. Some of these factors directly influence patient survival and treatment response [3,4].

Materials and Methods

A descriptive, observational, retrospective and prospective, single-center study was conducted at the Pierre and Marie Curie Center in Algiers over a six-year period, from January 2016 to December 2021.

Study Population

A total of 225 cases of exocrine pancreatic cancer at all stages were included. Patients were aged over 18 years and managed at the Medical Oncology Department of the Pierre and Marie Curie Specialized Hospital (EHS).

Inclusion Criteria

Patients with histologically confirmed exocrine pancreatic adenocarcinoma, based on surgical specimens or biopsy, regardless of tumor location within the pancreas, local or distant extension, and type of treatment received.

Exclusion Criteria

Absence of histological confirmation, endocrine pancreatic tumors, pancreatic malignancies other than adenocarcinoma (e.g., sarcoma, lymphoma), and mixed exocrine–endocrine tumors.

Statistics

Sample size calculation formula in a descriptive study:

The expected formula is:

$$n = z^2 \times p (1 - p) / i^2 \quad (1)$$

n = sample size

z = confidence level according to the normal distribution (for a standard 95% confidence level, z = 1.96)

p = estimated proportion of pancreatic cancer in the population = 9%

More Information

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i = tolerated margin of error (we aim to estimate the true proportion within 4%)

The calculated number of subjects is therefore 225 patients.

Univariate Analysis

Descriptive analysis of patient characteristics, including estimation of the mean, standard deviation, median, and quartiles for quantitative variables. Estimation of relative frequencies for qualitative variables, with their 95% confidence intervals and a 5% margin of error.

Analytical study of the relationships between patients and the different risk factors using statistical tests:

Use of the Chi-square (χ^2) test or Fisher's exact test for comparison of proportions. The difference between two proportions is considered statistically significant when $p < 0.05$, with estimation of the crude Odds Ratio (OR) and its confidence interval.

Use of the crude Odds Ratio (OR) with its 95% confidence interval to calculate morbidity risks.

Use of the ANOVA test for comparison of multiple means.

Use of the Student's t-test for comparison of means (quantitative tests).

Data Processing

Data entry was performed using Epi Info version 6.04d.

Data analysis was conducted using Epi Info version 6.04d and SPSS version 21.

Results

Characteristics of the Study Population

The proportion of patients with exocrine pancreatic cancer among all patients admitted to the center during the study period was 1.76%.

Risk Factors for Pancreatic Cancer

Non-Modifiable Factors

Age

The incidence of pancreatic cancer increases significantly with age, with most cases diagnosed after 60 years. Advanced age is often associated with a poorer prognosis due to the presence of comorbidities and reduced tolerance to aggressive treatments. The mean age in our population was 64.7 years (range: 20–92 years).

Sex

Males represented 52.9% of the population and females 47.1%, yielding a sex ratio of 1.12. A slight male predominance was observed, possibly related to greater exposure to environmental risk factors, particularly tobacco use. However, the direct impact of sex on survival remains moderate.

Personal Medical History

Eighty-eight percent of patients had significant medical histories. Diabetes mellitus was the most frequently observed comorbidity. Type 2 diabetes is both a risk factor and a potential early manifestation of pancreatic cancer. Long-standing diabetes increases cancer risk, whereas recent-onset diabetes may reflect advanced

disease at diagnosis, negatively affecting prognosis. Epidemiological studies indicate a 1.8-fold increased risk of PDAC in patients with type 2 diabetes, and diabetes is present in 40–60% of affected individuals. In our cohort, diabetes was observed in 57.5% of patients, predominantly type 2 (96.6%).

Chronic pancreatitis, particularly alcohol-related, is a well-established risk factor and is associated with an increased risk of malignant transformation and poorer prognosis due to pre-existing pancreatic damage. Long-standing chronic pancreatitis significantly increases the risk of PDAC. Hereditary pancreatitis, linked to PRSS1 gene mutations, carries an estimated 80-fold higher risk compared with the general population. In our study, 13% of patients showed imaging evidence of chronic pancreatitis; all were male, and half were smokers and alcohol consumers.

A personal history of digestive cancers, particularly those associated with genetic syndromes involving BRCA2 mutations, increases the risk of pancreatic cancer. Digestive cancer history was observed in 1.9% of patients. Non-digestive malignancies were reported in 7.7% of patients, including breast cancer (50%), prostate, endometrial, and thyroid cancers. Other medical histories included gastritis, gallstones, and cholecystectomy.

Family History

Although most cases are sporadic, 5–10% of patients report a family history of cancer. A family history of pancreatic cancer significantly increases risk, particularly when more than two first-degree relatives are affected. Key implicated genes include BRCA1, BRCA2 (relative risk 2–10), CDKN2A, and STK11. Hereditary forms may be diagnosed earlier, improving prognosis when appropriate surveillance is implemented. In our cohort, 16.7% of patients reported a family history of digestive malignancies.

Modifiable Factors

Obesity and Sedentary Lifestyle

Obesity, especially abdominal obesity, is associated with an increased risk of pancreatic cancer through mechanisms involving chronic inflammation and insulin resistance, which may worsen disease progression and reduce survival. Meta-analyses indicate a 10–50% increased risk with elevated body mass index. In our population, 27.1% of patients were overweight or obese.

Tobacco Use

Smoking is the most significant preventable risk factor for pancreatic cancer, increasing risk by approximately 75% compared with non-smokers. This elevated risk persists for at least 10 years after cessation and correlates with cumulative exposure. Passive smoking may increase risk by up to 50%. Smokers generally demonstrate reduced survival and poorer treatment response. In our cohort, 38.8% were active smokers.

Alcohol Consumption

Light to moderate alcohol intake (<4 drinks/day) has not been consistently associated with increased risk; however, heavy consumption is linked to higher risk. In our study, alcohol consumption was low and predominantly occasional.

Occupational Exposure

Exposure to ionizing radiation, pesticides, asbestos, nickel, chromium, and aromatic amines has been associated with pancreatic carcinogenesis in several studies.

Impact of Risk Factors on Survival and Prognosis

Pancreatic cancer is multifactorial and geographically heterogeneous. Prognosis depends primarily on stage at diagnosis, tumor resectability, and patient performance status. Risk factors influence these parameters directly or indirectly. Persistent modifiable factors such as smoking and obesity are associated with lower overall survival, whereas early identification of genetically high-risk individuals allows targeted surveillance and potentially improved outcomes.

Discussion

The analysis of risk factors supports the development of preventive strategies through risk reduction, lifestyle modification, and systematic health monitoring [5,6]. Early diagnosis may improve access to curative treatments. Although most cases are sporadic, reducing modifiable risks could lower disease incidence and improve prognosis [7-9]. Advances in genetics offer promising perspectives for early screening and personalized therapies. Public health strategies should prioritize smoking cessation, obesity prevention, and physician awareness for early diagnostic evaluation in high-risk individuals [10].

Conclusion

Pancreatic cancer remains a malignancy with poor prognosis, strongly influenced by multiple risk factors. Improving outcomes requires comprehensive epidemiological understanding, effective prevention strategies, and scientifically guided early detection programs to achieve meaningful clinical benefit.

Conflict of interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

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